

Guidelines for RDM monitoring within research institutes: Monitoring aspects and supporting tools

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Introduction

This document provides a list of metrics that can be used to measure compliance with various aspects of the [Radboud University RDM Policy](#). The objective of this document is to support the research institute's data stewards, who are responsible for having an overview of compliance of the RDM policy within their research institute¹. Data stewards are therefore the target audience for this document. This document is meant to provide ideas and inspiration, so you can choose the metrics or methods that are most relevant for your research institute. By measuring certain metrics regularly over time, they can be used in setting targets and measuring progress (key performance indicators, KPIs). Additionally, tracking these metrics allows one to observe changes in behaviour, calling attention to aspects that may require further support or highlighting what is going well.

Combining qualitative and quantitative metrics gives a more complete picture so the suggestions below have been split into those two categories. In general, quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) can more easily be collected while qualitative KPIs require more time investment from both the researcher and the data steward. We therefore recommend that quantitative KPIs be collected annually to be able to monitor progress, while qualitative KPIs be collected on a less frequent basis. In particular, certain moments may be opportune to touch base with researchers and collect qualitative KPIs, including onboarding meetings², annual meetings³, and exit reviews.

Future variations of this document hope to explore research software management.

¹ Of note, the primary responsibility for effective RDM and adherence to the RDM policy lies with the researchers.

² To introduce new researchers to the RDM policy, welcome packages can be used to highlight the policy as well as the RDM support services. Many data stewards meet with new PhDs for an onboarding session, which they use to inform them of the importance of RDM as well as tools and policy.

³ Ideally there would be a meeting that occurs each year with each researcher where information on RDM practices can be gathered. One example of an annual meeting is the annual review ('jaargesprek') however this meeting likely cannot be used for that purpose because of privacy reasons. Therefore, it may be fruitful to schedule an annual visit to research groups to gather said information.

Digital Competence Centre (DCC)

We would like to highlight that the DCC is here as a resource for the data stewards. The DCC can generate a number of the KPIs listed below for your research institute on a yearly basis.

Quantitative metrics

The benefit of quantitative KPIs is that they can often (semi-automatically/automatically) quickly be generated. While quantitative KPIs may not directly measure compliance, they can illustrate trends and patterns over the years.

If you would like to involve the researchers themselves in gathering the quantitative metrics, see the Healthy Data survey⁴ in the tools section below for ideas on closed-ended questions researchers could answer on how they manage their research data.

Below is a list of suggested quantitative metrics roughly divided by the phases of the research lifecycle.

Awareness & Engagement

- Number/percentage of researchers that are made aware of the research institute's RDM policy
 - Method: Number of researchers that are made aware of the research institute's RDM policy in an onboarding meeting or course for new researchers
- Number and type of RDM trainings organised per year
- Number of participants in each RDM training per year
- Number of consultations/hours for RDM support
 - Method: Number of appointments with researchers that data stewards have (e.g., estimate 45 minutes per appointment).
 - Method: Number of e-mails answered.
 - Method: Number of visits to research departments / guest lecture for courses to present on RDM.

Planning & DMPs

- Number of DMPs which were created and have text filled in
 - Method: DCC can generate these numbers annually per research institute if they use the RU DMP tool.
- Number/percentage of DMPs upon which feedback was requested (and additionally which percentage of those DMPs were modified after having received feedback)

⁴ Maya, A., De Oliveira Coelho Henriques, I., Pas, B.R. (2025): Research Data Management Practices and Challenges among Researchers in two Academic Institutions in the Netherlands. Version 2. Radboud University. (dataset). <https://doi.org/10.34973/6s67-q643>

- Method: DCC can generate these numbers annually per research institute if they use the RU DMP tool.
- Method: For Radboudumc, the number of DMPs that were shared with data stewards for review can be viewed in DMPonline.

Storage & security

- Numbers of projects with research data stored at a certified facility (e.g., workgroup folders, Teams, RDR)
 - Method: Include a question in an annual meeting or survey.
 - Method: Include a question in the exit interview to confirm no research data are on personal devices.
 - Method: The DCC can generate a list of DACs and RDCs in the RDR.
 - Method: Research institutes with a project system could track data storage facility requests.
- Number of data breaches or incident reports involving research data

Archiving & Publishing

- Number/percentage datasets archived/published in a trusted repository
 - Method: The DCC can generate a list of datasets that have been registered in Research Information System (RIS) and their respective repositories⁵.
 - Method: The DCC can generate a list of DACs and RDCs that have been archived in the RDR.
 - Method: Include a question in an annual meeting or survey asking where datasets are archived/published.
 - Method: Use of DataCite Commons, OpenAlex (see Tools below).
- Number/percentage of published articles that have a dataset associated with them
 - Method: Take a random sample of published articles and see if they have an archived/published dataset associated with them.
 - Method: Use Daniel's script (see Tools below) to see if the published article has a dataset associated with it.
 - Method: Research institutes with a project system could track the percentage of published articles that have a dataset associated with them.
 - Method: Check the RDM section in PhD theses based on research data.

Openness & FAIRness

- Number/percentage of dataset publications by access level
 - Method: The DCC can get the number/percentage of datasets per access level (e.g., open access, open access for registered users, restricted access) in the RDR.
- Number/Percentage of metadata of archived DAC and RDC that is public

⁵ Note that the Radboud Data Repository (RDR) datasets (called collections in the RDR) are automatically registered in RIS, however, many researchers do not register their datasets when archived/published elsewhere, so this will not be a complete picture of all datasets that are archived/published. If the data steward would like to look into this information themselves, they can use Data warehouse (see Tools below).

- Method: The DCC can generate this information.
- Number/percentage of dataset publications that have a DOI
 - Method: The DCC can generate a list of datasets that have been registered in RIS and have a DOI⁵.
- Number/percentage of datasets with a licence (e.g., CC-BY, CC0) or DUA
- FAIR score of datasets
 - Method: F-UJI, FAIRvaluator (see the Tools below).
- Number/percentage of researchers that have their ORCID registered in CRIS
- Number/percentage of datasets with researchers linked to ORCID
- Number/percentage of PhD theses based on research data with an approved RDM paragraph

Reuse & Impact

- Number of citations per datasets
 - Method: Use of DataCite Commons, Open Alex (see Tools below).
- Number of datasets downloaded or viewed
 - Method: The DCC can generate these numbers for datasets in the RDR.
 - Method: Repository themselves (e.g., DANS data stations, CLARIN B).
- Number of access requests for restricted access datasets
 - Method: The DCC can generate these numbers for datasets in the RDR.

Qualitative metrics

In addition to the quantitative metrics listed above, qualitative KPIs can provide valuable insights about researchers' experiences with RDM as well as their attitudes, challenges, and achievements. Combined, the qualitative and quantitative KPIs can provide a more complete picture.

There are various ways to collect qualitative KPIs including surveys, questionnaires, and interviews. See the Healthy Data survey⁶ in the tools section below for ideas on questions about how researchers manage their research data.

- Perceived usefulness of RDM support services
 - What do researchers appreciate and what are they missing?
 - Method: Short survey or interviews after consultations or trainings.
- Barriers to good RDM
 - What challenges do researchers face in implementing good RDM (e.g., publishing open access, writing a DMP, using ORCID, avoiding unauthorised storage locations).
 - Method: Short survey, question in an annual meeting.
 - Method: Include a question in a researcher's exit interview when researchers leave to make sure research data is not stored on personal

⁶ Maya, A., De Oliveira Coelho Henriques, I., Pas, B.R. (2025): Research Data Management Practices and Challenges among Researchers in two Academic Institutions in the Netherlands. Version 2. Radboud University. (dataset). <https://doi.org/10.34973/6s67-q643>

devices and if the researcher wants to use the research data once they leave, to formally arrange access with the research institute (e.g registered prolonged access or via a data sharing/transfer agreement).

- Method: If the RDM section in the PhD thesis based on research data needs to be approved by the data steward, make sure research data is not stored on personal devices.
- Case studies of good RDM practices
 - Methods: In-depth interviews with researchers.

Tools

Below are some tools that could be used for RDM monitoring:

- **Daniel's script:** For this script, you will need to download the pdfs of the published articles from your institute. The script searches for keywords (e.g. "data availability," "replication package") and returns the text found in those sections. The DCC can run the script for you if you send the pdfs and chosen keywords.
- **DataCite Commons:** A [platform](#) that allows for tracking datasets, including: citations, DOIs, and use of ORCID. However, they only have information about affiliation at the university level and not at the research institute level.
- **Data warehouse (DWH):** DWH displays information from RIS. Therefore it can generate a list of registered datasets and relevant information per research institute. Support staff can request access themselves to the tool and follow [manuals](#). However, the DCC is happy to provide metrics related to registered datasets from DWH.
- **DMP tool:** Radboud University has its own DMP tool, from which various metrics can be extracted. Metrics on number of DMPs that were created, the number of DMPs for which feedback has been requested, as well as the number of DMPs which were modified after having received feedback can be generated by the DCC.
- **Healthy Data survey:** The dataset '[Research Data Management Practices and Challenges among Researchers in two Academic Institutions in the Netherlands](#)' includes the results from the survey as well as the survey questions themselves, which can be reused to ask researchers how they manage their research data. Many of the questions are closed, making for quantitative metrics.
- **FAIRevaluator:** A [tool](#) to assess the FAIRness of digital resources using DOIs, handles, and URLs.
- **F-UJI:** [F-UJI](#), an Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool that allows you to fill in a dataset's identifier (URL, DOI, etc.) and will evaluate it on each of the FAIR principles and will return a score as well as an indication of which principles are met and which are not.
- **OpenAlex:** An open source [platform](#) that harvests information and could provide information on datasets from Radboud University. It can export search results as

a csv, which can be analysed. However, at the moment they are missing datasets (they are working on this) and they only have information about affiliation at the university level and not at the research institute level.

- **Radboud Data Repository (RDR):** Various metrics can be extracted from the RDR that assist in RDM monitoring. These include but are not limited to: the number of DACs and RDCs, how many of them are archived, and the number of views and downloads of published DSCs. The research administrator can gather these metrics, however the DCC can also generate these metrics for you.
- **TNW-tracking:** The first half of the [script](#) can be used to see how many researchers self-cite data/software. From a pilot done on output from one of the research institutes at RU, it appears that this happens quite infrequently. The second half of the script doesn't work for Radboud University since it relies on PURE, which the RU does not have.